

1 **Estimation of Post-death Interval in the Extreme North of Brazil – A Retrospective Study: A**
2 **Crucial Investigation into the Relationship Between Climatic Variables and Post-Death Interval in**
3 **the Amazon Region**

4
5 **Abstract:**

6 **Purpose:** This study aims to estimate the post-death interval (PDI) in autopsy cases in Roraima, Brazil, by
7 correlating climatic factors in a retrospective analysis conducted in the Amazon region, which features an
8 equatorial/tropical-humid climate. **Methods:** The data collection spanned from 2004 to 2019, focusing on
9 estimating the PDI alongside meteorological variables. Descriptive statistics included mean and standard
10 deviation (mean ± S.D.) for temperature, humidity, and precipitation, while inferential analysis applied the
11 Friedman-Nemenyi test to assess correlations between decomposition stages and variables such as missing
12 days, temperature, humidity, and precipitation. **Results:** The study encompassed 23 victims, revealing that
13 all examined variables significantly influenced the decomposition process. Humidity emerged as the most
14 influential factor, whereas precipitation exhibited the least impact on the putrefaction state. A statistically
15 significant relationship was observed between decomposition stages and the analyzed variables (missing
16 days, average temperature, humidity, and precipitation) ($p < 0.000000001$). Additionally, precipitation
17 correlated significantly with missing days ($p = 0.00766$) and average temperature ($p = 0.00001$). The
18 liquefaction stage was notably associated with average temperatures ranging from 26.1°C to 31.0°C and
19 humidity levels between 55.4% and 79.5%. Furthermore, precipitation played a role in this stage, as
20 evidenced by its correlation with missing days ($p = 0.00766$). **Conclusion:** Future research should prioritize
21 expanding data collection and integrating predictive models that incorporate a wider spectrum of
22 environmental parameters and case-specific conditions. This approach may refine PDI estimation accuracy,
23 enhancing forensic analyses in equatorial regions.

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43 Introduction:

44 Death can be defined as the irreversible cessation of bodily functions in the respiratory, circulatory,
45 and cerebral systems [1]. After this event, the corpse goes through a series of transformative decomposition
46 phenomena until it is finally reduced to a skeleton [2]. Although this process is continuous, studies divide
47 it into four phases, namely: (1) coloring/chromatic, (2) gaseous, (3) liquefaction, and (4) skeletonization
48 [2].

49 Post-mortem changes, such as the amount and distribution of rigor mortis, decrease in body
50 temperature, hypostasis, changes in the concentration of vitreous humor, entomological activity, and degree
51 of putrefaction occur successively, starting within hours and lasting for years [2,3]. For this reason, they
52 are factors used by forensic doctors to establish the post-death interval (PDI), that is, the time interval
53 between the moment of the individual's death and the detection of their corpse by the Scientific Police [3].
54 In this way, it is possible to estimate the moment of death of an individual [3] retrospectively.

55 Determining the PDI is challenging for forensic practice [1]. Numerous factors, such as
56 temperature conditions, air humidity, rainfall (occurrence levels), exposure of the body to the environment,
57 and chemical composition of the soil, can interfere in determining the putrefaction phases of a corpse.
58 Therefore, they can influence the temporal precision of the PDI [1,4]. Furthermore, individual endogenous
59 factors, such as pre-existing pathologies and histological characteristics of the organs, can also alter the
60 speed of cadaveric functionality phases and are unpredictable [1,3].

61 Since regional climatic conditions directly influence PDI, sequences of decomposition stages have
62 been proposed for specific geographic regions, such as some states in the interior of the United States of
63 America, such as Tennessee [5], New Mexico, Arizona, and Texas. However, the factors affecting these
64 locations differ from those in other geographic areas [6-7]. The literature has insufficient data for each
65 specific climatic condition or geographic area [8]. The same pattern is observed in the Brazilian context,
66 but literature is scarce [9].

67 When encountering unidentified bodies or victims of violence, Forensic Dentistry and Forensic
68 Medicine use the available information from the place of death to assist justice in determining the PDI.
69 Although several methods are described in the literature to help determine this period, they are all prone to
70 errors and precision. Therefore, each new method is potentially helpful for establishing PDI and may be
71 beneficial [1]. Thus, the objective of this work is to analyze the PDI estimate in necropsied victims in the
72 State of Roraima when considering climatic data through a retrospective study carried out in the extreme
73 north of the country (Amazon Region) and with an equatorial/tropical climate- damp.

74

75 Materials and Methods**76 a. Study design and sample**

77 A retrospective, observational study was carried out, with a comparative statistical procedure and
78 research technique using direct documentation in the field, through the survey of information contained in
79 anthropological expert reports dated from a period between 2004 and 2019 to analyze the estimation of the
80 post-mortem interval of bodies submitted to necropsy under specific climatic conditions in a region in the
81 extreme north of Brazil (Amazon Region). The research was conducted in accordance with the Declaration
82 of Helsinki and was approved by the Research Ethics Committee, under protocol number
83 81674224.0.0000.5374, on August 16, 2024.

84 b. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

85 The inclusion criteria for the study consisted of reports on victims of suspicious or violent deaths who
86 were autopsied at the Institute of Legal Medicine in Roraima (ILM/RR) in an advanced stage of
87 decomposition (gas phases, liquefaction, and skeletonization). Duly and fully completed reports of corpses
88 of both sexes, ethnicities, and age range of 07 - 75 years old were included in the study. Individuals whose
89 variables of interest did not have a description in the reports sufficient for evaluation were excluded.

90 c. Data collection

91 Data was collected in report files from the ILM/RR, the receiving unit, by a previously calibrated
92 examiner who selected the reports and organized the information together. The information extracted from
93 the expert reports consisted of the dates of the victim's disappearance and the date of entry of the body into
94 the ILM/RR, thus composing the number of days of the victims' disappearance, as well as the season of the
95 year in which the death occurred. The body's thanatological characteristics and the transformative
96 phenomenon phase were also collected.

97 Furthermore, a survey of the State of Roraima's regional climate was carried out using information
98 from the National Institute of Meteorology, Brazil's national meteorological organization
99 (<https://portal.inmet.gov.br/>). The research was carried out according to the weather conditions recorded on
100 the days in which the bodies were missing, using the city of Boa Vista, the capital of the State, as a reference
101 (<https://tempo.inmet.gov.br/CondicoesRegistradas>). Temperature, precipitation, and humidity data were
102 recorded in Greenwich Meridian Time (GMT) using automatic and conventional stations. The values
103 obtained from the date of the victim's disappearance until his arrival at the ILM/RR were tabulated and
104 transferred to Excel® (Redmond, Washington, USA). From this, the means and standard deviations of the
105 climatic variables were calculated for each case individually.

106

107 d. Statistical analysis

108 The data was processed using statistics. The descriptive analysis means the standard deviation (mean
109 \pm S.D.) for temperature, humidity, and precipitation variables.

110 The inferential analysis was carried out using the Friedman-Nemenyi test to verify the association
111 between the State of decomposition of the corpse and the variables: 1) missing days, 2) temperature, 3)
112 humidity, and 4) precipitation (H_0 = as missing days, temperature, humidity, and average precipitation do
113 not influence the State of decomposition of the bodies). The margin of error used in the statistical tests was
114 5%. The data were entered into the Excel® spreadsheet (Redmond, Washington, USA), and the program
115 used to obtain the statistical calculations was the R add-in for Excel Real Statics (Version 8.9.1, Copyright
116 2013- 2023 Charles Zaiortz www.real-statistics.com).

117

118 **Results:**

119 Twenty-three victims were included in the present study, of which 22 were exposed to the surface
120 with no signs of inhumation. Only one body was found buried. In six cases that went missing for three to
121 five days before being identified, five bodies (83.3%) showed characteristics of increased body volume,
122 two (33.3%) had hyperchromic integument, two (33.3%) detachment of integument, and one (16.6%)
123 hyperchromic face. One case (16.6%) also had blisters, and another (16.6%) had preserved integument with
124 an open abdomen. These characteristics led to the definition of the gas phase of transformative phenomena.
125 During periods of disappearance of these bodies, average temperatures varied from 24.349 °C (σ 246) to
126 29.757 °C (σ 3.47). Relative air humidity changed from 58.635% (σ 14.021) to 84.250% (σ 10.18), and
127 precipitation from 0 mm (σ 0) to 0.546 mm (σ 2.04) (Table 1).

128 Six cases were diagnosed in the liquefaction phase, with an interval of six to 22 days of
129 disappearance. Regression of body volume, dryness of epithelial tissue, and hyperchromic coloration were
130 present in two victims (33.3%). In one case (16.6%), there was desquamation of the epithelium, liquefaction
131 of muscle tissue, disorganized viscera, and a mass of putrilage. One case (16.66%), which was buried in
132 water, showed the presence of epithelial tissue, preservation of muscle tissue, and absence of viscera.
133 Regarding the local climate, average temperatures ranged from 26.112°C (σ 2.58) to 31.022°C (σ 2.90).
134 Relative air humidity indices changed from 55.386% (σ 14.80) to 79.489% (σ 11.82), and precipitation
135 rates from 0 (σ 0) to 14.53 mm (σ 20.06) (Table 2).

136 The skeletonization process was present in 11 victims, ranging from 5 to 86 days after
137 disappearance. The characteristics of bones/skeleton (100%) articulated (45.45%) or not (54.54%),
138 presence of remnants of epithelial tissue (18.18%) or muscular tissue (9.09%), and presence of mummified
139 tissue (18.18%). The average temperature ranged from 26.111°C (σ 2.57) to 30.104°C (σ 2.71). The

140 percentage of relative air humidity changed from 57.030% (σ 15.05) to 80.422% (σ 11.68), and the
141 millimeter of precipitation from 0 mm (σ 0) to 7.177 mm (σ 13.50) (Table 3).

142 The results showed that all tested variables influence the state of putrefaction of the body (Table
143 4); therefore, we reject H0. The air humidity variable proved the most relevant, and the precipitation
144 variable remained the least relevant to the bodies' putrefaction state (Table 5).

145 Table 6 displays the analysis of the variables combined in pairs. The combination of missing days
146 and average temperature was not statistically significant. All other two-by-two combinations of variables
147 were statistically significant.

148

149 **Discussion:**

150 The present study sought to analyze the PDI estimate in necropsied victims in the State of Roraima,
151 Brazil, when considering local climate data. The results reveal the complexity and importance of
152 environmental factors in the decomposition of bodies, with significant implications for forensic practice in
153 regions [2,10-11,13-14].

154 The results of the Friedman test, presented in Table 4, indicate a statistically significant difference
155 between the variables analyzed (days missing, average temperature, humidity, and precipitation) and the
156 state of putrefaction of the bodies ($p < 0.000000001$). This significance suggests that climatic factors,
157 together with the time of disappearance, influence the process of cadaveric decomposition.

158 Nemenyi's post hoc test, as shown in Table 6, identifies significant differences between various
159 combinations of variables. Specifically, humidity showed a substantial correlation with days gone ($p =$
160 0.00005) and mean temperature ($p = 0.03136$), indicating that high humidity levels can accelerate
161 decomposition. Precipitation was also significantly correlated with missing days ($p = 0.00766$) and average
162 temperature ($p = 0.00001$), suggesting that the presence of water, whether in the form of rain or immersion,
163 contributes to more decomposition. Other studies also imply that interactions between climate and cultural
164 factors such as clothes and scavengers [14] influence PDI.

165 The findings of this study are consistent with existing scientific literature on cadaveric
166 decomposition. Several studies [2,5,13-14] highlight the critical influence of environmental factors on the
167 decomposition rate and identify that ambient temperature is one of the main determinants of the
168 decomposition rate. Higher temperatures accelerate the chemical and microbial reactions that lead to
169 putrefaction. In tropical regions, such as the Amazon (State of Roraima), high temperatures associated with
170 high humidity can create ideal conditions for microbial and insect activity, accelerating cadaveric
171 decomposition. Giles et al. [13] also state that advanced decomposition is reached more quickly in humid
172 conditions.

173 The influence of humidity is also documented. In tropical-humid climates, such as Roraima, the
174 high relative humidity of the air facilitates bacterial and fungal activity, in addition to influencing the
175 presence and activity of scavenging insects, which are fundamental in the decomposition process [14].
176 Precipitation, on the other hand, can have a dual effect. In comparison, water can initially accelerate
177 decomposition by facilitating hydrolysis and putrefaction. However, prolonged immersion can lead to
178 saponification or partial body preservation under anaerobic conditions, as observed in studies of bodies
179 found in rivers or buried in saturated soil [12,14].

180 The results obtained have important implications for forensic practice in Roraima and other
181 regions with similar climates. A detailed understanding of the effects of temperature, humidity, and
182 precipitation on decomposition can assist forensic professionals in more accurately estimating PDI, which
183 is crucial for criminal investigations. The gas phase of decomposition, characterized by an intense increase
184 in body volume, was observed at average temperatures of 24.3°C to 29.8°C and air humidity of 58.6% to
185 84.2%. This information is consistent with the literature that states that temperatures above 20°C and high
186 air humidity accelerate the onset and progression of putrefaction [13-15].

187 Furthermore, the state of liquefaction, which begins between six and twenty-two days after death,
188 was associated with average temperatures between 26.1°C and 31.0°C and humidity ranging between

189 55.4% and 79%. This stage was influenced by precipitation, as demonstrated by the high p-value compared
190 to missing days ($p = 0.00766$). In comparative studies, regions with high rainfall tend to show more
191 accelerated decomposition, especially in bodies found in the open air or partially immersed [13-14].

192 Finally, in the skeletonization phase, more significant variability was observed in the post-mortem
193 interval, which ranged from five to eighty-six days. Average weather conditions for this phase included
194 temperatures of 26.1°C to 30.1°C and air humidity of 57.0% to 80.4%. The significant variation can be
195 attributed to different environmental conditions and body exposure, which influence the rate of
196 skeletonization.

197 Some limitations need to be overcome. No soil samples were collected; consequently, no analyses
198 were carried out. Although the ecology of soils associated with cadavers is poorly understood [6], in the
199 Brazilian context, soil collection and analysis are carried out by teams other than those that analyze the
200 bodies. The information is gathered in a judicial document called a police investigation, which is
201 confidential. At the end of the procedural process, data can be cross-checked. Still, due to the high volume
202 of work, it is not a standard operating procedure to carry out a retroactive analysis (retroactive data cross-
203 checking).

204 The study reinforces the need to consider local climatic factors when estimating the PDI, especially
205 in regions with an equatorial/tropical-humid climate, such as Roraima. The application of statistical tests
206 allowed the identification of significant relationships between states of decomposition and climatic
207 variables, offering a solid basis for improving forensic practices.

208 Future investigations should focus on collecting more comprehensive data and applying predictive
209 models that include a broader range of environmental variables and case-specific conditions. Improving
210 these methodologies will contribute to the accuracy of PDI estimation, thus strengthening criminal
211 investigations and justice.

212

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216 All authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest or funding issues in this research.

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222

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Table 1 Corpses in the gas phase - thanatological characteristics and regional climatic information.

Date of disappearance	ILM/RR input	Missing days	Thanatology - characteristics	Average temperature (°C)	Air humidity (%)	Precipitation (mm)
29/08/2011	01/09/2011	3	Intense increase in body volume.	28,478 (σ 4,01)	66,687 (σ 16,86)	0 (σ 0)
01/10/2018	04/10/2018	3	A body immersed in water (river), with a generalized increase in volume, blisters present, and hyperchromic integument.	29,757 (σ 3,47)	58,635 (σ 14,021)	0 (σ 0)
10/10/2011	14/10/2011	4	Generalized hyperchromic integument and increased body volume.	28,165 (σ 3,59)	72,400 (σ 15,22)	0,011 (σ 0,07)
28/08/2013	01/09/2013	4	Generalized detachment of integument and increase in body volume	24,349 (σ 2,46)	84,250 (σ 10,18)	0,546 (σ 2,04)
24/12/2018	28/12/2018	4	The body was partially immersed in water, with a hyperchromic face in brownish/blackish color, devoid of eyeballs, and an integument was preserved with an open abdomen.	27,050 (σ 2,89)	64,266 (σ 14,07)	0,010 (σ 0,07)
23/10/2011	28/10/2011	5	Generalized detachment of integument and increase in body volume.	26,734 (σ 3,28)	77,895 (σ 14,27)	0,220 (σ 0,96)

Table 2 Corpses in the liquefaction phase - thanatological characteristics and regional climatic information.

Date of disappearance	of ILM/RR input	Missing days	Thanatology – characteristics	Average temperature(°C)	Air humidity (%)	Precipitation (mm)
01/01/2015	07/01/2015	6	Return of body volume with generalized hyperchromic coloration, liquefying muscle tissue in the head and upper limbs.	28,333 (σ 3,31)	55,386 (σ 14,80)	0 (σ 0)
17/03/2005	25/03/2005	8	Desquamation of facial epithelial tissue, the beginning of the liquefaction phase.	29,200 (σ 3,01)	66,851 (σ 14,20)	3,1 (σ 7,28)
04/10/2007	12/10/2007	8	Decreased body mass volume, misshapen, covered by putrilage mass, dryness of epithelial tissue, and some skeletonized bone portions.	30,214 (σ 3,14)	68,703 (σ 12,73)	2,722 (σ 6,69)
03/09/2009	11/09/2009	8	Dry epithelium, brownish in color, and disorganized viscera.	31,022 (σ 2,90)	63,407 (σ 12,40)	0 (σ 0)
17/01/2015	29/01/2015	12	The body was immersed in water (river) in a state of liquefaction.	28,119 (σ 2,98)	59,099 (σ 14,00)	0,021 (σ 0,21)
19/05/2015	10/06/2015	22	Presence of epithelial tissue, conservation of muscle tissue, absence of viscera. Buried body.	26,112 (σ 2,58)	79,489 (σ 11,82)	14,530 (σ 20,06)

Table 3 Corpses in the skeletonization phase - thanatological characteristics and regional climatic information.

Date of disappearance	ILM/RR input	Missing days	Thanatology - characteristics	Average temperature(°C)	Air humidity (%)	Precipitation (mm)
26/11/2016	01/12/2016	5	Articulated skeleton, presence of remnants of muscular insertions (fibrous tissue).	29,308 (σ 3,49)	60,569 (σ 15,26)	0 (σ 0)
17/01/2004	24/01/2004	7	Skeletonized bones with articulated spine (child)	30,104 (σ 2,71)	62,333 (σ 11,61)	0 (σ 0)
21/12/2013	29/12/2013	8	Skeletonized bone (child).	27,702 (σ 2,77)	65 (σ 11,77)	0,333 (σ 0,70)
07/04/2009	20/04/2009	13	A large part of mummified epithelial integument, without viscera, the skeleton is still organized by the presence of joints.	29,942 (σ 2,99)	66,833 (σ 13,76)	4,071 (σ 12,41)
03/07/2015	17/07/2015	14	Bone with remnants of epithelial tissue in the chest, abdomen, and leg.	26,701 (σ 2,98)	76,108 (σ 13,68)	4,786 (σ 8,93)
17/12/2006	02/01/2007	16	Articulated skeleton, remnants of epithelial tissue in the thoracic region, and long bones.	29,621 (σ 2,78)	63,882 (σ 11,86)	0,117 (σ 0,48)
12/11/2016	01/12/2016	19	Disarticulated skeleton, except for the spine, with resected intervertebral discs. Presence of articular tissue at the ends of long bones.	28,997 (σ 1,29)	77,973 (σ 6,61)	1,33 (σ 3,12)
01/06/2019	27/06/2019	26	Skeletonized bones.	26,111 (σ 2,57)	80,422 (σ 11,68)	0,783 (σ 3,49)
28/07/2006	01/09/2006	35	Partially skeletonized bone, with mummified tissue in the thoracic region.	28,306 (σ 2,81)	78,185 (σ 12,25)	7,177 (σ 13,50)

17/02/2016	17/04/2016	60	Skeletonized bones.	29,480 (σ 3,13)	57,030 (σ 15,05)	0,067 (σ 1,09)
20/07/2009	14/10/2009	86	Skeletonized bones.	29,938 (σ 3,30)	70,099 (σ 14,94)	1,889 (σ 5,79)

Table 4 : p-value of the Friedman test for the analyzed variables and the state of putrefaction of the body.

Alpha	0,05
Q-stat	61,59130435
df	3
p-value	0,000000000

Table 5 Friedman-Nemenyi test for the relevance of the analyzed variables.

FRIEDMAN-NEMENYI TEST			Alpha 0,05		
Group	R sum	Size	Std err	q-crit	R-crit
Missing days	51	23			
Average temperature (°C)	66	23			
Air humidity (%)	90	23			
Precipitation (mm)	23	23			
		23	6,191392	3,633	22,49333

Table 6 p values from Nemenyi's post hoc test of the analyzed variables and the state of putrefaction of the body.

Q TEST

Group 1	Group 2	R sum	q-stat	p-value
Missing days	Average temperature (°C)	15	2,422719	0,31698
Missing days	Air humidity (%)	39	6,299068	0,00005
Missing days	Precipitation (mm)	28	4,522408	0,00766
Average temperature (°C)	Air humidity (%)	24	3,87635	0,03136
Average temperature (°C)	Precipitation (mm)	43	6,945127	0,00001
Air humidity (%)	Precipitation (mm)	67	10,82148	0,00000